

Being a Post truth woman, a foible?

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A comparative study of women protagonists from Vijay Tendulkar’s *Silence! The court is in session* and from Nikita Singh’s *The Promise*.

Abstract

*Humans are highly emotional creatures. More than any other system, emotions motivate us to respond to things quickly. This article, from and through literary characters, tries to cull out the vital role of women’s emotions and the consequences of those emotions which lead them to believe in post truth ideology as a flaw factor in their life. The characters Shambhavi from Nikita Singh’s *The promise* and Miss Leela Benare from Vijay Tendulkar’s *Silence! The court is in session* been studied to expose how their emotions are cheaply used to trap or fool them with post truth ideology by other characters, especially by the opposite gender in the text and to reveal their mishap moments in the text happens by their emotional response for post truth ideas.*

Sellers may know more than buyers about the quality of the items. It really matters, especially in communication, as speaker knows exactly about the things than a listener. In modern public life, a number of different varieties of nonsense where the precise facts are uttered or their veracity tend to be unimportant or irrelevant to the speaker to communicate. It’s not hard to see why the term post-truth emerged. Post-truth is framed to circumstances whereby objective facts are less influential in shaping the opinion of the public than appeals to personal belief and emotion. This post-truth is characterized by lies, propaganda and fake news and it is a hard task to find the meaning and truth in them. There were genuine reasons why it is important to sit down take a deep breath and pause for reflection while we are in a personal or public discourse. The main phenomena for the emergence of post-truth rooted in communication. Lying is uniquely a feature of our era. On this account, lying is bullshit; trying to deceive without lying is a bullshit; and the myriad forms of padding that are designed to impress, obfuscate or attract attention are also bullshit. There are certainly such things as facts for example the sun is shining and we need no one to persuade you. But from banal facts we always have to use judgment in deciding what a fact is and what to believe. Judgment almost plays a part in our decisions as to what is a fact and what is true. And unfortunately for the modern communicator, it turns out that lies are often unnecessary anyway; a remarkable

amount of powerful deception can be practiced without any lies being told. "It is a common error to confuse data with the truth: the former informs the latter, but they are not the same thing" said Matthew d'Ancona. This research papers tries to unfold the emotion of a women in differentiating truth and a lie and also take a brief tour about the different forms of emotional judgments of two women characters with mendacity in which facts are at issue, even though no direct lie is peddled. Where they are comfortable with near-lies and they often trapped in the form of lie that is not quite a direct lie.

Portrayal of women characters in lead has always been one of the most dominant preoccupations of all modern writers and finds its vivid and graphic manifestation in their work. The present article is a venture and modest attempt at hatching the lives of women, Shambhavi and Miss LeelaBenare, through their emotional judgment in order to embark upon the similarity of roller coaster of emotional judgments that leads them to a terrible suffering moments in their life from the romance fiction of Nikita Singh's *The promise* and in the drama of Vijay Tendulkar's *Silence!* The court is in session. As Richard A. Peterson states "comparison is one of the most powerful tools used in intellectual inquiry, since an observation made repeatedly is given more credence than in a single observation." This paper tries to make a comparative study of two women protagonist analyzing their behaviors, judgments and response after every emotions of theirs which leads to suffering and pain besides that it also works to cull out the kind of attraction of women towards post truth ideas. The two women leads whom we taken to analyze, Shambhavi and Miss LeelaBenare feel themselves as a Parrot but it is a powerful symbol of illusion of their own self and whereas sparrow represents their reality. This kind of illusion at moments is what made their life to a worse part. Women are known to be more emotional than men, with that in account, the decisions they take at the time of their emotion is mostly been a flaw in their life. Through feminism inevitably many vice things came into their account however then still certain emotion judgments has to be tinkered in a women's life. Even if both the characters were very educated, clever, bold and modern women but then their flaw in accepting eye washing words especially by men leads the readers to think critical about the women. Both the works has a similarity of men targeting women to suppress, subjugate, dominate and make use of them with their powerful use of words. The main flaw considered in those female characters would be the response and decisions they make after being emotional. The preference given to their personal belief and emotions hides the objective facts from their civilized minds.

Tendulkar crafted the character Miss LeelaBenare, as an educated and a working woman. She has been crafted as a bright, bold and confident woman. She very cleverly outfits the men and other characters of the play. She has been portrayed as an excellent school teacher who not only enjoys her work but also performs her duties perfectly. Miss Benare is not a traditional heroine who suffers the injustice by the society in the play. She is a new woman pleading for freedom from the social norms. Unfortunately she was in love with a university professor Mr. Damle, who was a married man and a father for two daughters, and carried his baby in her womb. The other characters, notably MrKashikar, took this situation for a mock trail and ask her to act as an accused. Since MrKashikar was an uneducated fellow elder than Miss Benare was jealous over her life style. He decides to trap Miss Benare with using selective words which gives the feel as just going to act a mock trail. In the beginning she was reluctant but then the cunning words of Mrkashikar made Miss Leela a lady of cheerful and free spirit is questioned about her sanctity. When the story moves on everyone starts to condemn her for her behaviors. She has trapped herself by being economical with the truths. She acted like as she doesn't know anything of that sort. The other main flaw has been the inability to figure out the indirect lies peddled in the sentences of MrKashikar considered being her main flaw. Silence in the play is a symbol of oppression, while speech signifies self-expression and liberation.

The silence refers to the act where Mr. Kashikar who acts as a judge refuses to listen to Miss Benare explanation and silences her again and again through indirect lies or pleasing words. Leena Benare refuses to be cowed down by men. The last speech of Miss Benare was skillfully constructed by Tendulkar. It echoes the irony, sorrow lampoon present in the reasoning mentality in Indian society. Ms Benare "But I was ignorant instead; I threw myself off a parapet of our house to embrace death. But I didn't die I felt as if my feelings were dead. The accusation turns into the verdict. Then the play turns from illusion to reality. But Benare remains in the same condition engrossed in thought for she is overtaken by the reality implied in the illusion. Her reality is different from others. This clearly reveals that women are infringed, women are exploited emotionally. The cynical game is well rooted in their sick psyche that informs the verdict they pass on her, with the sort of pleasure that can be envy of professional tortures.

Roller coaster rides of emotions were conveyed by Nikita through her lead character. Shambhavi, the beautiful portrayal of emotions, a girl who cherishes life, lives life to the fullest. She never shows her sorrows of life to others, sometimes she tries to hide them from herself too. Her world is limited to her father and friends. She leads a life of her own in an artistic way. After certain time, the readers could clearly see her peaceful life turning to turmoil by the decisions she takes in emotions. It again shows the incompetence of women in admiring to the mesmerizing words of men in a post truth sense. Arjun, a money minded, young, successful in his field enters into the life of Shambhavi. Fate chooses Shambhavi and Arjun to fall in love for each other. They followed the fate and very happy till Shambhavi got pregnant before the marriage. Arjun thought that she is being cheated by Shambhavi for his money and he left Shambhavi on his own. The unacceptable even nonsensical side of Shambhavi has been rooted clearly by the author. As of Benare, she too invites herself to the life of turmoil. The emotional feeling gives her space to accept whatever Arjun without second thought. She trusts him blindly even she knew he desperate for money making. Modern girl, civilized, well-educated but fails to reason to the logical facts.

The comparative study also finds out that a flaw of emotional response leads the story in which Miss Benare's and Shambhavi's private life is exposed and publicly dissected revealing that they are a woman of loose character. This also gives a clear view of the psychological violence that makes a female individual as helpless. It also displays how women are disrupted to do certain things. They cannot talk, walk and live freely. Even if they do, misfortune will inevitably fall upon their character. It is that it is also men who ruin the society but accused will remain women such as Shambhavi and Miss Leena Benare. Thus we see how the lies, propaganda and fake news in public society of which we just make a show are imposed only upon women and it is their responsibility to bear and follow it. Men however are free as culprits. Indian society being educated suffers due to the framed outlook of people which consists only of orthodox views and practices.

References

1. Tendulkar Vijay, *Silence! The court is in session*. Oxford University press, 1978.
2. Singh Nikita, *The Promise*. Penguin metro reads, 2014.
3. D'Anaconda Matthew, *Post-Truth*, Ransom house UK, 2017.
4. Davis Evan, *Post-Truth: Why we have reached peak bullshit and what we can do about it*, Little, Brown, 2017.
5. Bijay Kumar Dass, *Comparative literature*, Atlantic publishers, 2000.
6. Dhawan R.K., *Comparative Literature*, Behari Publication, 1987.